

Want a Good Social Analysis? Go to the Barbershop!

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Nowadays, social media is awash with quotes attributed to great historical figures. One such quote, often credited to Churchill, suggests:

"It is a pity that the people who know how to run the country are busy driving taxis and cutting hair."

Of course, the great Winston Churchill never actually said this; the line most likely belongs to the famous American comedian George Burns. However, the inaccuracy of the attribution does not diminish the wit and subtlety of the point: that perhaps the best political commentators are to be found in public spaces, specifically in taxis and barbershops.

Indeed, in British culture, the "barbershop" and the "black cab" are iconic symbols of public opinion exchange. This is a phenomenon prevalent not just in Britain, but in many other parts of the world, often serving as a staple of folk humour.

Perhaps younger readers might not be entirely familiar with this phenomenon. But for my generation (those over fifty, whom some might consider "prehistoric relics") the subject is all too familiar. I say "prehistoric" because for many of today's youth, history only began with the advent of social media and the internet; they find it hard to believe that someone's birth year could actually start with "19"!

Admittedly, things have changed. In many modern taxis, there is now a physical barrier between the driver and the passenger. The passenger effectively sits behind a glass partition and must press a button or use a microphone to speak to the driver. This physical

separation has turned the tradition of cabbie chat into something mechanical, stripping it of its traditional essence. Similarly, nowadays, barbers often wear wireless earbuds, spending the entire time talking to someone else on the other end of the line, while customers refuse to take their eyes off their smartphones. Given all this, I quite understand if you find this historical phenomenon hard to grasp.

You might wonder why, across the globe -from Iran where I grew up to Britain where I have grown old- barbers and taxi drivers are universally regarded as the best socio-political commentators, rather than members of any other profession.

The reason is simple: you cannot escape them.

When a barber drapes that cloth over your shoulders and slides the scissors through your hair, there is no escape; you are forced to sit patiently until they finish and set you free. Likewise, once the taxi door shuts and the driver pulls away, you are captive until the car stops. In both cases, you have no choice but to sit and listen patiently. Not only must you listen, but you must also nod in agreement, after all, it is hardly wise to argue with someone holding a razor and scissors, or the steering wheel and accelerator.

Furthermore, while sitting in that chair or cab, the distance between your ear and the speaker's mouth is barely a metre: the perfect opportunity for them to say whatever they wish and ask whatever they need. There is simply no escape.

But being a captive audience alone does not explain the "quality" of what you hear. The deeper reason lies elsewhere, and this is the true heart of the matter.

Barbers and cabbies are not merely talkers; they also ask questions and listen with great care and patience. What they tell you is, in

effect, the synthesis and distillation of the words of everyone who sat in that seat before you. They have heard it all, from the weather and the price of groceries to current politics, global shifts, and philosophical musings.

They begin by asking whether you live nearby, what you do for a living, or where you are from. Based on these data points, they decide which topic to engage you with. When I mention I am originally Iranian, they ask about the nuclear programme or the conflict with Israel; they ask a Ukrainian about the war with Russia, a Pakistani about the fate of Imran Khan, or an Indian about Virat Kohli and Priyanka Chopra. They know perfectly well that each of us follows the news of our homelands with meticulous attention. What better source for news on a distant conflict than someone directly living its consequences?

You might argue that being "up-to-date" is a quality shared by political analysts, university professors, and professional politicians, and that these might seem like better options than barbers or drivers. However, in my view, these tradespeople possess two invaluable qualities that academic experts often lack: they live "outside the bubble", and they stand on the "firm ground of reality".

We hear a great deal about the "bubble" of social media, how algorithms ensure we only ever encounter like-minded people. But the truth is that in recent years this bubble has extended well beyond our screens into our social lives and family circles; we effectively cut ties with anyone who thinks differently, sometimes even our own siblings.

The two professions I have described, however, cannot afford to live in a bubble. They cannot filter their customers based on political leanings or religious beliefs, nor can they turn away someone whose views they dislike. Why? Because they must put bread on the table, and, as the Persian proverb has it, "Bread is another name for God."

And so they must keep their ears open and their manner welcoming, to ensure that the customer leaves satisfied and comes back again.

To my mind, though, the most important quality these people possess is this: they always have their feet planted on the "firm ground of reality", and this is precisely what sets them apart from academics and professional analysts.

University professors are constantly engaged with raw data, books, academic journals, and learned colleagues. They undoubtedly know far more than ordinary people like me, but this can be hazardous in two distinct ways: it keeps them within an intellectual bubble, and it distances them from the lived, objective realities of the world around them.

Barbers and drivers, by contrast, interact with dozens of people every single day. They know what is happening under the skin of the city and society. They are familiar not just with the opinions of the masses, but with their personal experiences, their emotions, their daily struggles, and the cruel turns of fate that shape ordinary lives. They have their finger on the pulse of society; they sense when the community has a "fever"* and when it is "delirious." They know when people are afraid and when they have lost faith in their politicians.

Barbers and taxi drivers remind us that we, too, must always stand on the ground of reality. We have every right to theorise, to dream, and to wander through the heavens in our imaginations, so long as our feet remain planted on the earth. There is nothing wrong with gazing at distant horizons, provided we "never lift our feet from the ground"; for if we do, we will surely fall and be hurt.

That is why I believe it is in the queue, the taxi, the train, the bus, the underground, and the barbershop that we truly feel the pulse of

society, and learn things that no book or academic article could ever quite teach us.

And that is why I say to you: "if you want a good analysis, go to the barbershop".